

Title page

Title: Biocrust-forming mosses mitigate the impact of aridity on soil microbial communities in drylands: observational evidence from three continents.

Running title: Biocrusts regulate soil microbial resistance

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Summary

- Recent research indicates that increased aridity linked to climate change will reduce the diversity of soil microbial communities and shift their community composition in drylands, Earth's largest biome. However, we lack both a theoretical framework and solid empirical evidence of how important biotic components from drylands, such as biocrust-forming mosses, will regulate the responses of microbial communities to expected increases in aridity with climate change.
- Here we report results from a cross-continental (North America, Europe and Australia) survey of 39 locations from arid to humid ecosystems, where we evaluated how biocrust-forming mosses regulate the relationship between aridity and the community composition and diversity of soil bacteria and fungi in dryland ecosystems.
- Increasing aridity was negatively related to the richness of fungi, and either positively or negatively related to the relative abundance of selected microbial phyla, when biocrust-forming mosses were absent. Conversely, we found an overall lack of relationship between aridity and the relative abundance and richness of microbial communities under biocrust-forming mosses.
- Our results suggest that biocrust-forming mosses mitigate the impact of aridity on the community composition of globally distributed microbial taxa, and the diversity of fungi. They emphasize the importance of maintaining biocrusts as a sanctuary for soil microbes in drylands.

Key words. Drylands, Bacteria, Fungi, Biodiversity, Microbial composition, Aridity.

Introduction

The diversity and composition of soil microbial communities are implicated in the regulation of almost every terrestrial ecosystem function and service, including nutrient cycling, climate regulation, organic matter decomposition and plant production (Jing et al. 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016a; 2017). A growing body of experimental and observational results indicate that global environmental drivers such as land use change, nitrogen (N) enrichment and climate change are impacting upon both microbial diversity and community composition in terrestrial ecosystems (Gans et al. 2005; Garcia-Pichel et al. 2013; Maestre et al. 2015). For example, a recent global assessment of microbial communities demonstrated that increases in aridity will reduce the diversity of fungi and bacteria and drive shifts in their community structure in global drylands (Maestre et al. 2015). Thus, any impacts of increasing aridity on soil microbial communities can potentially have important consequences for the provision of ecosystem services in terrestrial environments (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016a). Drylands are crucial to achieve global sustainability, as they cover ~45% of Earth's land surface (Právělie et al. 2016), support over 38% of the global human population (Reynolds et al. 2007), harbour a very rich and unique biodiversity (Maestre et al. 2012) and play critical roles in the global carbon (C) cycle (Poulter et al. 2014). The global significance of drylands is going to increase due to climate change, as forecasted increases in aridity worldwide will expand the global extent of drylands by up to 23% by the end of this century (Huang et al. 2016). Therefore, understanding how increasing aridity affects soil microbial communities, and how different ecosystem features may modulate such impacts, is essential to develop new mitigation and adaptation strategies to climate change.

Drylands are highly heterogeneous ecosystems that are typically formed by a matrix of discrete vegetation patches embedded in a matrix of open areas devoid of perennial vegetation (Valentin et al. 1999). These open areas are commonly occupied by soil surface communities dominated by cyanobacteria, mosses and lichens (biocrusts hereafter), which are one of the most widespread and important biotic components in drylands worldwide (Lindo & Gonzalez 2010; Belnap et al. 2006). Biocrust-forming mosses, like plants (e.g. Prober et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2016; 2017), provide habitat for soil organisms, including bacteria and fungi that thrive in the soil beneath them (Kuske et al. 2012; Steven et al. 2013), and largely influence their abundance and activity (Bates et al. 2010; Miralles et al. 2012; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b). A growing number of experiments are providing evidence that microbial communities associated with biocrusts (e.g. cyanobacteria) are highly vulnerable to climate change from local to regional scales (Reed et al. 2012; Garcia-Pichel et al. 2013; Ferrenberg et al. 2015). Previous studies have also highlighted the role of biocrusts in promoting the resistance and resilience of soil functioning (e.g. nutrient cycling) to climate change (Reed et al. 2012; Delgado-

Baquerizo et al. 2014; 2016b; Liu et al. 2016). However, despite the acknowledged importance of biocrust-forming mosses for ecosystem functioning (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b), we know little about how they impact the composition and diversity of microbial communities across environmental gradients. Indeed, and to the best of our knowledge, no study to date has explicitly addressed the role of biocrust-forming mosses in regulating the response of microbial communities to increasing aridity at a continental scale.

Herein we present a conceptual model of microbial responses to changes in aridity under two different microsites: biocrusts and bare ground (Fig. 1). In our model, shifts in community composition (i.e., relative abundance of microbial taxa) and diversity (i.e., richness: number of phylotypes) in response to increases in aridity are relatively small in biocrust-forming mosses compared to bare ground microsites (Fig. 1). Therefore, our conceptual model predicts that, compared with open areas without visible biocrust constituents (i.e. bare ground), biocrust-forming mosses should reduce any fluctuations in the richness and composition of microbial communities caused by increasing aridity (Fig. 1). The rationale underpinning our model is that biocrust-forming mosses provide habitat that is more conducive to microbial growth and survival than bare ground (Baran et al. 2015). For example, well-developed biocrust-forming mosses often have roughened surfaces that, in some ecosystems, trap water, allowing them to maintain humid conditions for longer and buffering extreme environmental conditions typical of drylands (Eldridge et al. 2010; Berdugo et al. 2014; Chamizo et al. 2016). Further, biocrust-forming mosses provide a reliable and consistent supply of resources such as C and N for microbial communities, which may promote their resistance to increasing aridity. Finally, we clarify that our approach explicitly assumes that naturally occurring patches of bare ground and biocrusts are the drivers of microsite amelioration rather than reflecting pre-existing conditions. Such an assumption is supported by previous experimental studies providing evidence that biocrusts modulate the response of soil microbes and microbially-driven functions to global change drivers (Reed et al. 2012; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013a; Liu et al. 2016; 2017).

To test our conceptual model, we conducted a field survey covering two microsites (bare ground and biocrust-forming mosses) in 39 locations from three continents (North America, Europe and Australia) across a wide aridity gradient (from arid to humid ecosystems), and characterized bacterial and fungal communities in the soil surface using the Illumina Miseq profiling of ribosomal genes and internal transcribed spacer markers, respectively. In addition, we used four surrogates of ecosystem functions linked to C, N and phosphorus (P) cycling (total N, activity of β -glucosidase, activity of phosphatase and available P) to evaluate the relationships between microbial composition/richness and ecosystem functioning along aridity gradients.

Methods

Study sites and data collection

We collected field data from 39 sites located in USA, Spain and Australia (Fig. S1; Table S1). Locations for this study were chosen to represent a wide aridity gradient; we included arid (aridity index = 0.05-0.20; n = 6 sites), semiarid (aridity index = 0.20-0.50; n = 24 sites), dry-subhumid (aridity index = 0.50-0.65; n = 4 sites) and humid (aridity index > 0.65; n = 5 sites) ecosystems. To improve interpretation, aridity was presented as 1-Aridity Index [AI], where AI = precipitation/potential evapotranspiration (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2013b). This alters the aridity scale such that sites with higher aridity values are more arid. Aridity index data were obtained from the global aridity map of the FAO (<http://www.fao.org/geonetwork/srv/en/main.home?uuid=221072ae-2090-48a1-be6f-5a88f061431a>). The selected sites included grasslands, shrublands, savannas, dry seasonal forests and open woodlands dominated by trees. Mean annual precipitation and temperature and soil pH of the study sites ranged from 140 to 1167 mm, from 8.1 to 19.5° C, and from 4.6 to 8.4, respectively.

Data collection was carried out between July 2012 and March 2014 according to a standardized sampling protocol (Maestre et al. 2012b). At each site, we established a 30 m × 30 m plot representative of the dominant vegetation. All soils were collected during the dry-season (July 2012 in the USA, July 2013 in Spain, March 2014 in Australia) to reduce bias among study sites due to seasonal changes in the soil variables studied. To the best of our knowledge, the sampled areas did not undergo dramatic climatic changes within this timeframe. At each site, a composite sample (from three 0-5 cm deep cores) was collected under the most common biocrust-forming mosses, and in bare ground; this is naturally occurring (i.e. non-disturbed) open areas devoid of perennial vegetation and without visible biocrust constituents. We maintained a minimum separation distance of 1 m between samples or away from perennial plant patches to remove potential sources of dependence among samples (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b). A total of 78 soil samples were analyzed for this study. After field sampling, biocrust-forming mosses and plant roots were carefully separated from the soil, which was sieved (2 mm mesh) and separated into two fractions. One soil fraction was immediately frozen at -20 °C for quantifying the diversity and community composition of bacteria and fungi in our samples. The other fraction was air-dried and stored for one month before biogeochemical analyses.

We focused on biocrust-forming mosses because they are globally distributed (in boreal, arctic, temperate and dryland ecosystems) and are commonly found across wide environmental gradients worldwide (e.g. from humid to arid systems; Lindo & Gonzalez, 2010), and because they contribute directly or indirectly (i.e. through cyanobacterial associates) to critical ecosystem functions, including nutrient cycling, soil stability, infiltration and gas exchange (Eldridge et al., 2010; Lindo & Gonzalez,

2010). The most common biocrust-forming mosses in our study sites were *Syntrichia caninervis*, *Syntrichia ruralis* and *Bryum* spp. (USA), *Pleurochaete squarrosa*, *Tortula revolvens*, *Weissia* sp. and *Bryum* spp. (Spain) and *Desmatodon convolutus*, *Barbula calycina*, *Didymodon torquatus* and *Rosulabryum* spp. (Australia). In the Australian plots, where this data was available, the cover of biocrust-forming mosses naturally increased with aridity as open spaces become more available and plant cover decreased (Fig. S2).

Assessing microbial diversity and composition

In this study, we worked with microbial diversity (number of phylotypes) at the OTU (i.e. operational taxonomic units) level and community composition at a higher level of taxonomic classification (i.e. phyla). The main reasons to work with community composition of bacteria and fungi at the phylum level are: 1) the main phyla are globally distributed and common across samples, allowing us to directly compare our soil samples across continents (e.g. Ramirez et al. 2012); 2) the use of a high level of taxonomic classification is suggested as an appropriate method of predicting broad patterns in ecosystem functioning (Philippot et al. 2010), and 3) functional information has become increasingly available at the phylum level (Fierer et al. 2007; Trivedi et al. 2013). For example, the richness and relative abundance of major microbial phyla representatives (e.g., Actinobacteria, Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes) have been recently reported to strongly regulate soil multifunctionality in microcosm experiments (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2017).

Molecular analyses were separately conducted on composite samples of each microsite (bare ground and biocrust-forming mosses) pooled within a site (two samples per site). Soil DNA was extracted from 0.5 g of defrosted soil samples using the Powersoil® DNA Isolation Kit (Mo Bio Laboratories, Carlsbad, CA, USA) according to the instructions provided by the manufacturer. The extracted DNA samples were frozen and shipped to the Next Generation Genome Sequencing Facility of the Western Sydney University (Australia), where they were defrosted and sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq platform (Caporaso et al. 2012) and the 341F/805R (bacteria; Herlemann et al. 2011) and FITS7/ITS4 (fungi, Ihrmark et al. 2012) primer sets (See Methods S1 for bioinformatic analyses). We kept main bacterial and fungal taxa (i.e. bacterial and fungal phyla accounting for >95% of relative abundance; Fig. S3) and richness (number of OTUs at a 97% similarity threshold) for further analyses.

Surrogates of soil functions

We used four variables related to C, N and P cycling and storage as surrogates of ecosystem functioning (functions, hereafter): available P, total N, activity of β -glucosidase and phosphatase. Overall, these variables constitute good proxies of processes driving nutrient cycling, biological productivity, and the buildup of nutrient pools (Maestre et al. 2012). Soil total N was measured with a

CN analyzer (Leco CHN628 Series, Leco Corporation, St Joseph, MI, USA). Phosphatase and β -glucosidase activities were measured as described in Maestre et al. (2012). The concentration of Olsen inorganic P was measured from NaHCO_3 0.5M soil extracts, as described in Delgado-Baquerizo et al. (2016b).

Statistical analyses

We first explored the “effects” of biocrust-forming mosses on microbial community composition and richness (number of OTUs at a 97% sequence similarity). To do this, we calculated the relative interaction index (RII) for each site and microsite as $(\text{Micr}_{\text{bio}} - \text{Micr}_{\text{bg}})/(\text{Micr}_{\text{bio}} + \text{Micr}_{\text{bg}})$, where Micr_{bio} and Micr_{bg} are values of microbial richness and relative abundance of main microbial phyla under the biocrust-forming mosses and in bare ground areas for a given site, respectively (Armas *et al.*, 2004). This index provides the relativized difference between biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground microsites. We then compared the average (across sites) values of RII of each of the evaluated microbial variables between these microsites. Values of this index ranged from -1 to +1, with positive values indicating increases in microbial diversity/ relative abundance of main taxa under the canopy of biocrust-forming mosses compared to bare ground, and negative values the opposite.

We then used a non-metric multidimensional ordination (NMDS) to explore the overall effects of microsite (biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground) and aridity conditions on bacterial and fungal community composition (i.e. relative abundance of all bacterial and fungal phyla), respectively. The two-dimensional NMDS solution, using Euclidean distance, provided a suitable representation of both the bacterial and fungal community NMDS data. Prior to these analyses, data were log-transformed to reduce the influence of extreme values. We conducted NMDS analyses with the PRIMER v6 statistical package for Windows (PRIMER-E Ltd., Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK) using the Euclidean distance.

Our conceptual model assumes that microsite modulates the effects of aridity on bacterial and fungal community composition (Fig. 1). This implies an interaction between aridity class (arid, semiarid, dry-subhumid and humid) and microsite (biocrust-forming mosses vs. bare ground), which requires statistical validation prior to analyses. Therefore, we explicitly tested for this interaction using a two-way MANOVA, with aridity class and microsite as fixed factors. In these analyses we focused on phyla that represent >95% of the relative abundance of fungal and bacterial communities, respectively. We found a strongly significant aridity class x microsite interaction for the composition of both bacteria ($F = 1.67$, $P < 0.001$; Fig. S3) and fungi ($F = 1.88$, $P = 0.003$; Fig. S4). Once we had provided evidence of microsite-dependency in the response of microbial community to climate change, we explored the impacts of different aridity classes (i.e. arid, semiarid, dry-subhumid and humid) on microbial

composition, independently, for each microsite. To do this, we conducted a one-way ANOVA with aridity class as a fixed factor for the relative abundance of each microbial phyla studied and for the diversity of both bacteria and fungi. Moreover, we repeated these analyses using a more conservative approach. We examined the effects of aridity classes on microbial variables by conducting a nested ANOVA, with aridity classes as a fixed factor and country (Australia, Spain and USA) as a random factor nested within aridity classes, respectively (Quinn & Keough, 2002). These analyses were conducted independently for each microsite. This approach aims to control for any effect of the geographical location (country) in our analyses.

In addition, we used linear regressions to determine the relationship between aridity (1 – Aridity Index) and both microbial composition (NMDS axes 1 and 2 and the relative abundance of main phyla) and richness. Separate analyses were conducted for bare ground and biocrust-forming mosses microsites. We further repeated these analyses, but evaluating the linear regressions between aridity (1- aridity index) and the residuals of the different microbial variables (non-metric multidimensional scaling [NMDS] axes, relative abundance of main phyla and microbial richness) for bare ground (bare) and biocrust-forming mosses microsites. Residuals for microbial variables were obtained from a one-way ANOVA with country (Spain, Australia and USA) as a fixed factor. These analyses are carried out separately for bare ground (bare) and biocrust-forming mosses microsites. The main goal of these analyses was to reduce the influence of any unexplained variation that might arise from the fact that samples were collected in different countries. The resulting residuals from these ANOVAs were therefore not influenced by country selection (see Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016c for a similar approach).

Moreover, to statistically evaluate whether the relationship between aridity and the main bacterial and fungal phyla followed a similar trend in both the biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground, we explored the interaction between microsite and aridity class using a linear model for each of the analyzed microbial variables. If, as hypothesized, biocrust-forming mosses regulate the response of microbial taxa to increasing aridity, we would expect to find either no relationship or a lower slope in the relationship between aridity and each microbial variable in biocrust-forming mosses compared with areas of bare ground. To further explore differences in the response of microbial composition and diversity in biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground, we calculated the coefficient of variation across sites for microbial diversity and the relative abundance of each of the evaluated phyla (Tilman et al. 2014).

Finally, to evaluate how possible shifts in microbial composition could affect ecosystem functioning, we calculated the correlations (Spearman's rank) among microbial community

composition/richness and the surrogates of soil functions evaluated (available P, total N and activity of β -Glucosidase and phosphatase). Correlations and ANOVA analyses were performed using SPSS 15.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Data accessibility

Data associated with this paper have been deposited in figshare: <https://figshare.com/s/e459fe6097cf9fa9c845> (10.6084/m9.figshare.5782263).

Results

Soils from this study were dominated by the bacterial phyla *Actinobacteria* and *Proteobacteria*, and by the fungal phylum *Ascomycota* (Fig. S3). Biocrust-forming mosses had an overall positive effect, as measured with the RII index, on the relative abundance of *Armatimonadetes*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Cyanobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Proteobacteria*, *Verrucomicrobia* and on fungal diversity, and a negative effect on the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria* (Fig. 2). This was particularly evident in the most arid locations (Fig. S4). Conversely, biocrust-forming mosses had no overall effect on either bacterial diversity or the relative abundance of main fungal taxa (Fig. 2). In general, biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground areas had similar fungal composition but, on average, biocrust-forming mosses had a slightly higher relative abundance of undetermined taxa, an outcome that was particularly evident in the most arid locations (Fig. S5). Biocrust-forming mosses also had a much lower and higher relative abundance of *Basidiomycota* than bare ground in the most humid and arid locations, respectively (Fig. S5).

The first axis of the NMDS conducted with bacterial phyla (Fig. 3a) was strongly positively related to the relative abundance of *Proteobacteria* (Spearman $\rho = 0.67$; $P < 0.001$) and *Acidobacteria* (Spearman $\rho = 0.47$; $P < 0.001$), but negatively related to the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria* (Spearman $\rho = -0.71$; $P < 0.001$) and *Chloroflexi* (Spearman $\rho = -0.68$; $P < 0.001$), while the second NMDS axis (Fig. 3a) was positively related to *Planctomycetes* (Spearman $\rho = 0.60$; $P < 0.001$). Similarly, the first axis of the NMDS conducted with fungal phyla (Fig. 3b) was strongly negatively related to the relative abundance of *Ascomycota* (Spearman $\rho = -0.90$; $P < 0.001$) and positively related to *Basidiomycota* (Spearman $\rho = 0.83$; $P < 0.001$) while the second NMDS axis (Fig. 3b) was positively related to Unidentified phyla (Spearman $\rho = 0.91$; $P < 0.001$) and negatively related to the relative abundance of *Zygomycetous* fungi (Spearman $\rho = -0.52$; $P < 0.001$).

We found significant relationships between aridity and the first axis of the Bacterial and Fungal NMDS ordinations (-), fungal richness (-) and the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria* (+), *Proteobacteria* (-), *Planctomycetes* (-), *Acidobacteria* (-), *Chloroflexi* (+), *Gemmatimonadetes* (+),

Verrucomicrobia (-), *Ascomycota* (+), *Zygomycota* (-) in the bare ground microsite (Table 1; Figs. 3c and d, S6-S8). However, these relationships disappeared when analyzing data collected under biocrust-forming mosses. The slopes of the relationships between aridity and all microbial composition and diversity variables were steeper for bare ground than for biocrust-forming mosses (see aridity x microsite interaction in Table 1; Figs 3; Figs. S5-6). This was particularly notable for the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria*, *Proteobacteria*, *Chloroflexi*, *Verrucomicrobia* and *Ascomycota* (Table 1; $P < 0.05$). In support of this, the coefficient of variation of the first NMDS axis of bacterial and fungal phyla, and that of the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria*, *Proteobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Acidobacteria*, *Chloroflexi*, *Gemmatimonadetes*, *Verrucomicrobia*, *Ascomycota* and fungal richness along the aridity gradient was always lower under biocrust-forming mosses than in bare ground (Table 1). In general, we found similar results when we explored the relationships between aridity and the residuals of microbial variables –controlled by country– (Table S2), *i.e.* we found that the slopes of the relationships between aridity and all microbial composition and diversity variables were steeper for bare ground than for biocrust-forming mosses (Table S2).

Similarly, we only found significant differences among aridity conditions for the relative abundance of *Proteobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Acidobacteria*, *Chloroflexi*, *Gemmatimonadetes*, *Verrucomicrobia*, *Ascomycota* and *Basidiomycota* for bare ground, but not for biocrust-dominated, microsites (Fig 4; Table S2). Interestingly, the largest shifts in the relative abundance of the microbial communities studied occurred from dry-subhumid to semiarid, and from semiarid to arid ecosystems (Fig 4; Table S3). Aridity had similar effects on the second NMDS axis conducted with fungal phyla and on the relative abundance of *Bacteroidetes* (+), *Armatimonadetes* (+), *Cyanobacteria* (+), *Basidiomycota* (-) and *Unidentified* fungal phyla (+) in both bare ground and biocrust-dominated microsites (Table 1; Figs. S6, 7 and 9). However, the relationship between aridity and the relative abundance of *Armatimonadetes*, *Basidiomycota* and *Unidentified* fungal phyla still had a lower slope and coefficient of variation in the biocrust-forming mosses than the bare ground microsites. We also found similar results when using the nested ANOVA to evaluate the effects of aridity classes on the relative abundance of major taxa in the two microsites evaluated (Table S3 vs. S4). Again, we found an overall larger effect of aridity classes on the microbial variables in bare ground areas than under biocrust-forming mosses microsites (Table S4).

We found that the diversity and relative abundance of several microbial phyla were positively related to surrogates of soil functions. The relative abundance of these taxa were negatively correlated with aridity on bare ground areas, but not under biocrust-forming mosses. For example, the diversity of fungi, and the relative abundance of *Acidobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Basidiomycota* and

Gemmatimonadetes were positively correlated with total N and the activity of β -glucosidase (Table 2). We note that, in the Australian sites, where these data were available, the concentration of total N was highly positively correlated with dissolved inorganic N, total available N (dissolved inorganic and organic N), microbial biomass N and N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase (an enzyme related to N cycle; Fig. S10). Fungal richness and the relative abundance of *Verrucomicrobia*, *Basidiomycota* and *Zygomycota* were positively related to the activity of phosphatase. Finally, the relative abundance of *Gemmatimonadetes* and fungal unidentified phyla, which peaked in the most arid locations and under biocrust-forming mosses microsites, was positively correlated to the availability of P in soil (Table 2).

Discussion

Our results, from an observational cross-continental survey, suggest that biocrust-forming mosses have the potential to mitigate the impact of aridity on the composition of soil bacterial and fungal communities, and on the diversity of fungi, in drylands. In particular, increasing aridity altered the relative abundance of the majority of microbial communities (~90% and ~60% for bacteria and fungi, respectively) including *Actinobacteria*, *Proteobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Acidobacteria*, *Chloroflexi*, *Gemmatimonadetes*, *Verrucomicrobia*, *Ascomycota*, *Zygomycota* and fungal richness on areas of bare ground. However, increasing aridity had a much lower influence on the community composition and diversity of soil microbes under biocrust-forming mosses. Most importantly, the slopes of the relationships between aridity and all the microbial composition and diversity variables evaluated were steeper for bare ground than for biocrust-forming mosses, suggesting the presence of greater stability in these microbial features across the aridity gradient under biocrust-forming mosses. Together, our results suggest that biocrust-forming mosses have the potential to buffer the negative effects of aridity on the relative abundance of the main bacterial and fungal phyla.

Several mechanisms could explain the observed lack of relationship between aridity and the richness and/or community composition of soil bacteria and fungi along the aridity gradient for biocrust-forming mosses *cf.* bare ground microsites. For example, biocrusts are known to modify microclimate, infiltration and soil water availability dynamics compared with adjacent crust-free surfaces (Almog and Yair 2007; Eldridge et al. 2010; Berdugo et al. 2014; Chamizo et al. 2016; but see Bowker et al. 2013). Increasing aridity is a major threat to microbial community composition (i.e. relative abundance of main taxa) and diversity in drylands (Maestre et al. 2015). Therefore biocrust-forming mosses could potentially buffer some of the negative effects of aridity on microbial composition by maintaining higher water availability for longer after rainfall events, and by providing a refuge for bacterial and fungal communities in drylands. Interestingly, the only reported overall

negative effect of biocrust-forming mosses on the relative abundance of microbial taxa was found on *Actinobacteria* (Fig. 2), which are highly resistant to desiccation (Battistuzzi and Hedges 2009), as evidenced by its dominance in bare ground areas under the most arid conditions. Thus, dominant *Actinobacteria* taxa might prefer drier environments (Maestre et al. 2015) and be suppressed by other microbial communities as soil moisture increases under biocrust-forming mosses. Another mechanism explaining our results is related to the capacity of biocrust-forming mosses to promote “fertility islands” in drylands, enhancing atmospheric carbon and nitrogen fixation and phosphorus desorption from bedrock compared to adjacent bare ground areas (Concostrina-Zubiri et al. 2013; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b). Thus, by providing a constant source of resources (carbon inputs e.g. via photosynthetic processes and moss decomposition) and holding soil moisture for longer after rainfall events, biocrust-forming mosses may promote the stability of soil microbial communities to conditions of increasing aridity.

Our results suggest that biocrust-forming mosses might buffer the negative impacts of aridity on key functional microbial groups such as *Acidobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Verrucomicrobia* and *Basidiomycota*, and on the diversity of fungi (Fierer et al. 2007; Trivedi et al. 2013, Wagg et al. 2014; Jing et al. 2015; Maestre et al. 2015). These microorganisms were highly positively associated with multiple surrogates of ecosystem functions, including soil enzyme activities (linked to decomposition), total N and available P (Table 2). They may also play a critical role in the decomposition of litter originating from the mosses themselves (Hagemann and Moronic 2015). Bacterial and fungal phyla such as *Acidobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Verrucomicrobia* and *Basidiomycota* have a large capacity to degrade a range of organic C compounds (Fierer et al. 2007; Trivedi et al. 2013). Similarly, fungal richness may also play an important role in breaking down litter from biocrust-forming mosses. This is supported by a growing number of studies highlighting the role of microbial diversity in supporting soil processes such as nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition (Wagg et al. 2014; Jing et al. 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016a).

Given the overall lack of change of microbial community composition and diversity to increasing aridity under reported biocrust-forming mosses, our results suggest that compared with bare ground, biocrust-forming mosses may buffer reductions in soil fertility that are likely to result from a drying climate (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013b). The area occupied by biocrust-forming mosses is often higher in semiarid and arid areas due to reductions in competition from a dwindling vascular plant cover (Fig. S2) and therefore to the greater potential area for colonisation and growth resulting from reduced plant cover (e.g. Belnap et al. 2001; Thomas et al. 2011; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b). Recent experimental studies have also found that the area occupied by mosses may also expand

with warming (Ladrón de Guevara et al. 2018). However, biocrusts are highly sensitive to physical disturbance associated with grazing (Eldridge et al., 2010; Kuske et al. 2012), and to other human activities such as agriculture (Zaady et al. 2016). In this respect, any negative impacts of physical disturbance on biocrust-forming mosses may result in a reduction in microbial resistance, and thus on the resultant goods and services that they provide (e.g. soil fertility). It is imperative, therefore, that any disturbance to biocrusts is minimized, particularly in the most arid areas.

Finally, it is important to note that our results only consider the role of biocrust-forming mosses in regulating the response of microbial community composition and richness to increases in aridity. Our choice of biocrust type was due to their ubiquity in drylands (biocrust-forming mosses are globally distributed and present across multiple biomes; Lindo & Gonzalez, 2010; Elbert et al., 2012), practicality and influence on ecosystem functioning (Eldridge et al., 2010; Lindo & Gonzalez, 2010). The sign (positive) of the effects of mosses on microbial stability reported here might be shared across other biocrust types such as lichens, have been previously reported to promote both soil microbial activity and functioning previously (Liu et al. 2017). However, it is also probable that the magnitude of the positive effects from biocrusts on soil microbial stability are dependent upon the identity of biocrusts, as recent studies point to species-specific effects on soil functions and microbial abundance in biocrust communities (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016b; Liu et al. 2016).

Together, our results provide observational evidence that aboveground biotic communities have the potential to regulate the responses of soil microbial community composition and diversity to increases in aridity. In particular, we found an overall lack of relationship between aridity and the relative abundance and richness of main microbial taxa in biocrust-forming mosses compared to bare ground microsites. The often reported positive effect of biocrust-forming mosses on moisture and resource availability may explain, in part, our results. Microbial taxa beneath biocrust-forming mosses that are relatively unresponsive to aridity include key functional microbial phyla such as *Acidobacteria*, *Planctomycetes*, *Verrucomicrobia* and *Basidiomycota*. Effects were also greatest on the diversity of fungi, which are known to play important roles in providing a highly functional environment below biocrust-forming mosses. Together our results emphasize that it is critically important to establish effective policies and management practices to protect these organisms. This will not only reduce the risk of soil erosion and therefore land degradation and subsequent desertification, but will ensure that dryland microbial communities are able to function effectively and support key ecosystem services in a warmer, and more arid, world.

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Author contributions

M.D-B. designed this study. Field samplings were conducted by M.D-B., D.J.E., M.A.B. and F.T.M. Lab analyses were done by F.T.M and M.D-B. Sequencing analyses were provided by B.K.S. Bioinformatic analyses were done by T.C.J. Statistical modeling was done by M.D-B. The manuscript was written by M.D-B with contributions from all co-authors.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Figure 1. *A priori* conceptual framework exploring how biocrust-forming mosses modulate the effects of aridity on soil microbes. Biocrust-forming mosses (vs. bare ground) promote microbial

resistance in response to climate change by buffering reductions in soil humidity and resource availability derived from increasing aridity. Thus, we expect lower shifts in main microbial taxa and diversity across different aridity conditions in biocrust-forming mosses compared to bare ground microsites.

Figure 2. Effects of biocrust-forming mosses, as measured with the RII index, on bacterial (a) and fungal (b) composition (relative abundance of main phyla) and diversity (OTU richness). Values represent means \pm 90% bootstrap confidence intervals ($n = 39$). Relative abundance data for biocrust and bare ground microsites are available in Figs. S2-4.

Figure 3. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots showing the relative differences in community composition of soil bacteria (a) and fungi (b) for biocrust-forming mosses (circles) and bare ground (triangles) microsites along the aridity gradient studied. Lower panels show the relationship between aridity and the first axis from the NMDS of soil bacteria (c) and fungi (d) in biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground microsites, respectively. Solid and dashed lines represent linear regressions fitted to biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values for these regressions are available in Table 1. Data in panels (a) and (b) are mean values \pm SE ($n = 39$).

Figure 4. Relative abundance of main bacterial (A-F) and fungal (G-H) phyla in biocrust-forming mosses and bare ground microsites across different aridity conditions. Data represents means \pm SE, n as follows: humid (n = 5), dry-subhumid (n = 4), semiarid (n = 24) and arid (n = 6). Different letters

indicate significant differences between aridity conditions ($P < 0.05$; post-hoc tests after one-way ANOVA). Analyses were done independently for bare ground and biocrusts microsites (see Table S3 for full ANOVA results).

Table 1. Summary results of linear regressions between aridity (1-Aridity Index) and different microbial variables (non-metric multidimensional scaling [NMDS] axes, relative abundance of main phyla and microbial richness) for bare ground (bare) and biocrust microsites. Interaction between aridity and microsite was calculated using a two-way MANOVA. $P \leq 0.05$ in bold.

Microbial variable	Bare				Biocrust				Interaction	
	R ²	Slope	P	CV(%)	R ²	Slope	P	CV(%)	P	
Bacterial NMDS 1	0.564	-3.399	<0.001	48.46	0.001	-0.103	0.863	30.643	<0.001	
Bacterial NMDS 2	0.009	0.412	0.546	28.382	0.027	0.492	0.322	19.143	0.925	
Fungal NMDS 1	0.246	-2.425	0.001	70.208	0.004	-0.220	0.691	45.684	0.003	
Fungal NMDS 2	0.359	1.269	<0.001	21.684	0.224	2.324	0.002	46.502	0.170	
Bacterial richness	0.006	255.3	0.636	17.874	0.004	220.600	0.717	19.648	0.966	
Fungal richness	0.098	-322.1	0.052	29.122	0.053	-234.200	0.158	25.996	0.702	
Actinobacteria	0.134	13.122	0.022	25.659	0.029	-4.924	0.298	24.808	0.015	
Proteobacteria	0.411	-21.538	<0.001	30.061	0.037	-4.830	0.238	21.445	0.006	
Planctomycetes	0.171	-10.069	0.009	29.574	0.025	-3.030	0.340	21.291	0.147	
Acidobacteria	0.175	-8.939	0.008	30.166	0.048	-4.617	0.180	28.704	0.355	
Chloroflexi	0.358	19.673	<0.001	51.678	0.064	6.086	0.121	41.166	0.022	
Gemmatimonadetes	0.197	4.815	0.005	47.291	0.045	1.974	0.193	42.831	0.197	
Bacteroidetes	0.138	3.166	0.019	63.33	0.267	7.624	<0.001	71.133	0.072	
Verrucomicrobia	0.387	-5.379	<0.001	53.052	0.022	-0.731	0.366	27.552	0.001	
Armatimonadetes	0.365	2.096	<0.001	59.615	0.280	1.347	<0.001	40.656	0.198	
Cyanobacteria	0.199	3.317	0.004	96.63	0.199	6.583	0.004	115.354	0.184	
Ascomycota	0.113	29.236	0.036	27.641	0.064	-20.175	0.120	26.752	0.009	
Basidiomycota	0.350	-47.218	<0.001	56.297	0.121	-23.28	0.030	48.164	0.109	
Unidentified fungi	0.395	23.666	<0.001	79.51	0.318	46.366	<0.001	125.351	0.066	
Zygomycota	0.307	-20.369	<0.001	142.194	0.039	-10.432	0.227	178.821	0.318	

Table 2. Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ) between microbial attributes (bacterial and fungal composition and diversity) and four surrogates of ecosystem functions (total N, phosphatase, glucosidase and available phosphorus; n = 78).

Taxa	Parameters	Glucosidase	Total N	Phosphatase	Olsen P
<i>Acidobacteria</i>	ρ	0.354	0.285	0.107	-0.082
	P-value	0.001	0.011	0.350	0.477
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	ρ	-0.337	-0.120	0.089	0.049
	P-value	0.003	0.296	0.439	0.669
<i>Bacteroidetes</i>	ρ	0.355	-0.076	-0.308	0.425
	P-value	0.001	0.509	0.006	<0.001
<i>Chloroflexi</i>	ρ	-0.111	-0.204	-0.309	0.152
	P-value	0.332	0.073	0.006	0.183
<i>Cyanobacteria</i>	ρ	0.109	-0.162	-0.328	0.343
	P-value	0.340	0.157	0.003	0.002
<i>Planctomycetes</i>	ρ	0.528	0.660	0.107	0.088
	P-value	<0.001	<0.001	0.351	0.445
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	ρ	-0.249	-0.219	0.183	-0.347
	P-value	0.028	0.054	0.109	0.002
<i>Verrucomicrobia</i>	ρ	0.211	0.186	0.430	-0.252
	P-value	0.064	0.103	<0.001	0.026
<i>Gemmatimonadetes</i>	ρ	0.414	0.244	-0.034	0.508
	P-value	<0.001	0.032	0.764	<0.001
<i>Armatimonadetes</i>	ρ	-0.048	-0.331	-0.229	0.249
	P-value	0.678	0.003	0.044	0.028
Bacterial richness	ρ	0.533	0.447	0.163	0.361
	P-value	<0.001	<0.001	0.154	0.001
<i>Ascomycota</i>	ρ	-0.128	0.060	0.140	0.067
	P-value	0.264	0.600	0.221	0.558
<i>Basidiomycota</i>	ρ	0.037	0.269	0.379	-0.285
	P-value	0.745	0.017	0.001	0.012
<i>Unidentified fungi</i>	ρ	0.196	-0.194	-0.671	0.503
	P-value	0.085	0.088	<0.001	<0.001
<i>Zygomycota</i>	ρ	-0.045	0.157	0.374	-0.286
	P-value	0.698	0.171	0.001	0.011
Fungal richness	ρ	0.311	0.392	0.458	-0.006
	P-value	0.006	<0.001	<0.001	0.957

Supporting Information

Article title: Biocrusts mitigate the impact of aridity on soil microbial communities in drylands: evidence from observations across three continents.

Authors: Manuel Delgado-Baquerizo, Fernando T. Maestre, David J. Eldridge, Matthew A. Bowker, Thomas C. Jeffries & Brajesh K. Singh.

The following Supporting Information is available for this article:

Methods S1. Bioinformatic analyses.

Table S1. Location, aridity index and aridity class of the study sites.

Table S2. Summary results of linear regressions between aridity and the residuals of the different microbial variables for bare ground and biocrust microsites.

Table S3. Results of one-way ANOVAs testing the effects of aridity class on microbial composition and diversity in bare ground and biocrust microsites.

Table S4. Results of one-way nested ANOVAs testing the effects of aridity class on microbial composition and diversity in bare ground and biocrust microsites.

Figure S1. Locations of the study sites in USA (n = 8), Spain (n = 10) and Australia (n = 21).

Figure S2. Relationships between aridity and the cover of biocrusts (A) and plants (B) in the 21 locations from Australia. Panel (C) includes the relationship between the cover of biocrusts and plants in the studied plots.

Figure S3. Relative abundance of major bacterial and fungal phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Data represent mean values for soil samples across USA, Spain and Australia (n = 39).

Figure S4. Relative abundance of major bacterial phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites across different aridity conditions. Data represents means, n as follows: humid (n = 5), dry-subhumid (n = 4), semiarid (n = 24) and arid (n = 6).

Figure S5. Relative abundance of major fungal phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites across different aridity conditions. Data represents means, n as follows: humid (n = 5), dry-subhumid (n = 4), semiarid (n = 24) and arid (n = 6).

Figure S6. Relationships between aridity and the relative abundance of main bacterial taxa in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust

and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S7. Relationships between aridity and the relative abundance of four main fungal taxa (a-d) in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1. Unidentified = Unidentified fungi.

Figure S8. Relationships between aridity and the richness of bacteria (a) and fungi (b) in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S9. Relationships between aridity and the second axis of the nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination conducted with soil bacteria (a) and fungi (b). Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S10. Relationship between total N and dissolved inorganic N (DIN), total available N (dissolved inorganic and organic N), microbial biomass N and N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase in the 21 plots from Australia.

Methods S1. Bioinformatic analyses. Initial sequence processing and diversity analyses for both bacterial 16S rDNA and fungal ITS genes were conducted using the QIIME package (Caporaso *et al.* 2010). Initially, low quality regions ($Q < 20$) were trimmed from the 5' end of sequences and paired ends were joined with FLASH (Magoč & Salzberg 2011) for 16S rDNA sequences and Fastq-join (Aronesty 2011) for ITS reads. Sequences were de-multiplexed and a further round of quality control was conducted to remove sequences containing ambiguous bases (N), and reads containing bases with a quality score below 25. Chimeric 16S rDNA sequences were detected using the UCHIME algorithm from the USEARCH package (Edgar *et al.* 2010; 2011) implemented within VSEARCH (<https://github.com/torognes/vsearch>). The RDP training dataset V950 was used as a reference for chimera detection, as recommended by the UCHIIME documentation. De Novo (abundance based) chimera detection was used for ITS data using USEARCH (Edgar *et al.* 2010). The remaining high quality chimera free sequences were used for downstream analysis. Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) were defined as clusters of 97% sequence similarity using UCLUST (Edgar *et al.* 2010). Taxonomy was assigned using UCLUST (Edgar *et al.* 2010) against the Greengenes database version 13_850 (DeSantis *et al.* 2006; Mcdonald *et al.* 2012) for 16S rDNA OTUs. For fungal ITS sequences, taxonomy was assigned using BLAST (Altschul *et al.* 1990) against the UNITE database V6.9.754 ($E < 10^{-5}$). The resultant OTU abundance tables for both primer sets were filtered to remove singletons and rarefied to an even number of sequences per samples to ensure an equal sampling depth (11925 and 17000 for 16S rDNA and ITS respectively). Bacterial and fungal richness was calculated on these rarefied OTU tables using QIIME (Caporaso *et al.* 2010).

Table S1. Location, aridity index and aridity class of the study sites.

Site	Country	Latitude	Longitude	Aridity index	Aridity class
1.000	Australia	-34.998	145.726	0.303	Semiarid
2.000	Australia	-34.254	146.071	0.298	Semiarid
3.000	Australia	-33.910	150.994	0.661	Humid
4.000	Australia	-33.982	151.057	0.799	Humid
55.000	Australia	-34.358	146.209	0.319	Semiarid
57.000	Australia	-34.415	146.309	0.319	Semiarid
60.000	Australia	-34.284	146.576	0.332	Semiarid
62.000	Australia	-34.435	147.423	0.442	Semiarid
65.000	Australia	-34.744	149.888	0.566	Dry-subhumid
71.000	Australia	-33.655	150.862	0.763	Humid
72.000	Australia	-33.622	150.771	0.715	Humid
76.000	Australia	-34.363	148.919	0.573	Dry-subhumid
77.000	Australia	-33.981	148.948	0.615	Dry-subhumid
79.000	Australia	-33.834	148.609	0.513	Dry-subhumid
81.000	Australia	-33.506	148.173	0.474	Semiarid
85.000	Australia	-33.730	148.203	0.491	Semiarid
92.000	Australia	-33.324	148.164	0.455	Semiarid
100.000	Australia	-34.506	150.239	0.712	Humid
BU1	Australia	-34.128	142.084	0.188	Arid
BU2	Australia	-34.159	142.338	0.216	Semiarid
CY28	Australia	-33.845	147.388	0.402	Semiarid
Best Friends	USA	37.113	-112.552	0.240	Semiarid
Boundary	USA	38.174	-109.710	0.143	Arid
Bridges	USA	37.582	-109.910	0.234	Semiarid
Church Wells	USA	37.086	-111.697	0.140	Arid
Kodachrome	USA	37.507	-112.022	0.204	Arid
Monticello	USA	37.730	-109.414	0.289	Semiarid
NorthWash	USA	38.003	-110.517	0.116	Arid
Should	USA	37.758	-111.443	0.154	Arid
Barrax	Spain	39.049	-2.230	0.367	Semiarid
C. Real	Spain	40.327	-3.424	0.381	Semiarid
Carrascoy	Spain	37.799	-1.304	0.268	Semiarid
Morata	Spain	40.209	-3.418	0.381	Semiarid
Ontigola	Spain	39.993	-3.623	0.376	Semiarid
S. Espuña	Spain	37.822	-1.672	0.297	Semiarid
Titulcia	Spain	40.186	-3.503	0.337	Semiarid
Villarobledo	Spain	39.209	-2.514	0.369	Semiarid
Yecla	Spain	38.588	-1.204	0.395	Semiarid
Zorita	Spain	40.355	-2.878	0.446	Semiarid

Table S2. Summary results of linear regressions between aridity (1-aridity index) and the residuals of the different microbial variables (non-metric multidimensional scaling [NMDS] axes, relative abundance of main phyla and microbial richness) for bare ground (bare) and biocrust microsites. Residuals for microbial variables were obtained from a one-way ANOVA with country (Spain, Australia and USA) as a fixed factor. These analyses are independently done bare ground (bare) and biocrust microsites. The main goal of these analyses was to reduce the noise derived from the fact that samples were collected in different countries in our analyses. Thus, the residuals from these ANOVAs were not influence by country selection.

Microbial variable	Bare			Biocrust		
	R ²	Slope	P	R ²	Slope	P
Bacterial NMDS 1	0.283	-2.891	<0.001	0.148	-2.089	0.016
Bacterial NMDS 2	0.049	1.196	0.178	0.023	0.83	0.353
Fungal NMDS 1	0.088	-1.611	0.067	0.021	-0.788	0.378
Fungal NMDS 2	0.069	1.423	0.107	0.000	-0.099	0.913
Bacterial richness	0.002	0.223	0.804	0.019	0.754	0.399
Fungal richness	0.005	-0.394	0.661	0.003	-0.275	0.76
Actinobacteria	0.041	1.097	0.217	0.040	1.081	0.225
Proteobacteria	0.339	-3.164	<0.001	0.205	-2.46	0.004
Planctomycetes	0.141	-2.036	0.019	0.049	-1.202	0.176
Acidobacteria	0.072	-1.46	0.098	0.006	-0.433	0.63
Chloroflexi	0.186	2.343	0.006	0.910	1.635	0.062
Gemmatimonadetes	0.118	1.867	0.032	0.175	2.271	0.008
Bacteroidetes	0.001	-0.133	0.882	0.004	-0.336	0.708
Verrucomicrobia	0.111	-1.811	0.038	0.022	-0.798	0.372
Armatimonadetes	0.094	1.662	0.058	0.071	1.446	0.101
Cyanobacteria	0.192	2.38	0.005	0.008	0.476	0.596
Ascomycota	0.059	1.318	0.136	0.007	0.454	0.612
Basidiomycota	0.093	-1.659	0.059	0.028	-0.914	0.305
Unidentified fungi	0.114	1.833	0.036	0.011	0.558	0.533
Zygomycota	0.114	-1.836	0.035	0.000	0.067	0.941

Table S3. Results of one-way ANOVAs testing the effects of aridity class (arid, semiarid, dry-subhumid and humid) on microbial community composition (i.e. relative abundance of main taxa) and diversity in bare ground and biocrust microsites.

	Bare			Biocrusts		
	Mean Square	F	P	Mean Square	F	P
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	65.019	1.653	0.195	29.167	1.104	0.361
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	298.215	21.589	0.000	67.263	4.210	0.012
<i>Planctomycetes</i>	63.593	4.184	0.012	21.370	1.913	0.146
<i>Acidobacteria</i>	44.511	3.674	0.021	4.920	.326	0.806
<i>Chloroflexi</i>	181.428	8.173	0.000	24.778	1.366	0.269
<i>Gemmatimonadetes</i>	15.526	5.591	0.003	4.567	1.755	0.174
<i>Bacteroidetes</i>	2.913	1.273	0.299	20.991	3.630	0.022
<i>Verrucomicrobia</i>	14.918	11.255	<0.001	0.156	0.188	0.904
<i>Armatimonadetes</i>	2.199	9.505	0.000	.873	5.759	0.003
<i>Cyanobacteria</i>	5.647	3.907	0.017	23.523	4.203	0.012
Bacterial richness	720641.780	2.333	0.091	1080344.022	2.847	0.052
<i>Ascomycota</i>	673.042	3.261	0.033	460.549	2.525	0.073
<i>Basidiomycota</i>	1030.275	7.685	0.000	222.136	1.622	0.202
<i>Unidentified</i>	271.291	10.351	0.000	1678.579	18.200	0.000
<i>Zygomycota</i>	226.502	8.181	0.000	243.303	3.195	0.035
Fungal richness	94583.073	3.284	0.032	101209.736	3.696	0.021

Table S4. Results of one-way nested ANOVAs testing the effects of aridity class (arid, semiarid, dry-subhumid and humid) on microbial composition (i.e. relative abundance of main taxa) and diversity in bare ground and biocrust microsites. In these analyses, country (Spain, Australia and USA) is a random factor nested within aridity class.

		Bare			Biocrusts		
		Mean Square	F	P	Mean Square	F	P
Actinobacteria	Biome	68.315	0.888	0.521	5.595	0.070	0.973
	Country (Biome)	94.068	2.749	0.059	104.673	5.484	0.004
Proteobacteria	Biome	250.146	7.413	0.048	33.130	0.635	0.636
	Country (Biome)	42.823	3.86	0.018	68.664	6.221	0.002
Planctomycetes	Biome	35.837	0.385	0.773	10.694	0.177	0.906
	Country (Biome)	128.682	28.229	<0.001	82.928	18.655	<0.001
Acidobacteria	Biome	10.694	0.177	0.906	19.692	0.464	0.726
	Country (Biome)	82.928	18.655	<0.001	56.231	7.047	0.001
Chloroflexi	Biome	124.475	3.883	0.099	18.218	0.661	0.614
	Country (Biome)	36.551	1.753	0.176	31.826	1.888	0.152
Gemmatimonadetes	Biome	13.411	2.201	0.237	1.485	0.459	0.723
	Country (Biome)	7.604	3.271	0.034	3.526	1.402	0.260
Bacteroidetes	Biome	2.408	0.312	0.818	12.551	0.367	0.783
	Country (Biome)	10.204	6.599	0.001	47.095	24.656	<0.001
Verrucomicrobia	Biome	12.865	11.978	0.004	0.372	0.803	0.515
	Country (Biome)	0.959	0.706	0.556	0.297	0.338	0.798
Armatimonadetes	Biome	0.872	2.352	0.206	0.413	0.777	0.574
	Country (Biome)	0.434	2.045	0.127	0.705	7.073	0.001
Cyanobacteria	Biome	7.374	2.614	0.190	5.966	0.578	0.660
	Country (Biome)	3.448	2.741	0.059	12.481	2.521	0.075
Bacterial richness	Biome	478752.871	0.665	0.612	648818.779	0.934	0.494
	Country (Biome)	802547.122	3.274	0.024	757972.020	2.293	0.082
Ascomycota	Biome	557.881	4.586	0.025	101.915	0.199	0.892
	Country (Biome)	83.069	0.381	0.767	662.236	4.820	0.007
Basidiomycota	Biome	870.346	6.370	0.029	183.374	2.562	0.095
	Country (Biome)	137.799	1.031	0.392	41.806	0.287	0.835
Unidentified fungi	Biome	375.468	2.696	0.212	382.286	0.914	0.524
	Country (Biome)	190.803	17.704	<0.001	567.046	11.884	<0.001
Zygomycota	Biome	217.658	17.721	<0.001	235.851	4.293	0.042
	Country (Biome)	5.265	0.177	0.911	45.283	0.573	0.637
Fungal richness	Biome	43412.766	1.008	0.464	61379.277	3.613	0.073
	Country (Biome)	45943.161	1.728	0.169	14891.113	0.514	0.726

Figure S1. Locations of the study sites in USA ($n = 8$), Spain ($n = 10$) and Australia ($n = 21$).

Figure S2. Relationships between aridity and the cover of biocrusts (A) and plants (B) in the 21 locations from Australia. Panel (C) includes the relationship between the cover of biocrusts and plants in the studied plots.

Figure S3. Relative abundance of major bacterial and fungal phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Data represent mean values for soil samples across USA, Spain and Australia (n = 39).

Figure S4. Relative abundance of major bacterial phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites across different aridity conditions. Data represents means, n as follows: humid (n = 5), dry-subhumid (n = 4), semiarid (n = 24) and arid (n = 6).

Figure S5. Relative abundance of major fungal phyla in bare ground and biocrust microsites across different aridity conditions. Data represents means, n as follows: humid (n = 5), dry-subhumid (n = 4), semiarid (n = 24) and arid (n = 6).

Figure S6. Relationships between aridity and the relative abundance of main bacterial taxa in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S7. Relationships between aridity and the relative abundance of four main fungal taxa (a-d) in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1. Unidentified = Unidentified fungi.

Figure S8. Relationships between aridity and the richness of bacteria (a) and fungi (b) in bare ground and biocrust microsites. Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S9. Relationships between aridity and the second axis of the nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination conducted with soil bacteria (a) and fungi (b). Solid and dashed lines represent fitted linear regressions in biocrust and bare ground microsites, respectively. Slope, R^2 and P values of these regressions are available in Table 1.

Figure S10. Relationship between total N and dissolved inorganic N (DIN), total available N (dissolved inorganic and organic N), microbial biomass N and N-acetyl-β-glucosaminidase in the 21 plots from Australia.

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